

Robot-Assisted Training Scaffolds Narrative Organization and Sequencing Abilities in Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder: A Randomized Controlled Trial

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Supplementary Materials

S1. Standard therapy

All participants received regular therapy recognized by the Italian National Health Service (Servizio Sanitario Nazionale, SSN). Treatment is multidisciplinary, involving professionals such as psychomotor therapists, speech and language therapists, occupational therapists, and special educators, under the supervision of a child neuropsychiatrist who coordinates individualized clinical plans. Therapy goals are personalized according to each child's developmental profile and clinical priorities, which may target social, communication, or autonomy skills depending on functional level and family needs. The frequency and intensity of sessions vary according to DSM-5 level of required support, so that children with higher support needs typically attend several sessions per week, while those with milder profiles receive less intensive schedules.

S2. Measures of interest

BVSCO-3 is a standardized clinical test used to assess writing and orthographic skills in children aged 6–14 years. Among its subtests, the Written Narrative Production task was selected, as it requires participants to produce a short story based on a series of visually presented stimuli. In this task, the child must organize a set of picture sequences into a coherent story and write a narrative describing the events in temporal and causal order. This task was here used as an index of autonomy-related cognitive skills, such as action planning and the ability to organize goal-directed behaviour. This choice is consistent with the Model of Expressive Writing proposed by Cornoldi et al. (2010), where it is theorized that successful narrative composition depends on the ability to plan and structure ideas hierarchically, monitor ongoing performance, and revise output, processes that reflect the executive and metacognitive skills underpinning autonomous behaviour in daily life. Therefore, improvements in this test were considered indicative of enhanced capacity to plan, integrate, and regulate their own expressive output, reflecting potential transfer effects of the autonomy-oriented intervention.

The NEPSY-II is a comprehensive neuropsychological assessment battery for children aged 3–16 years. Within its Memory and Learning domain, the Narrative Memory subtest was administered to measure memory for organized verbal material under three recall conditions: Free recall, Cued recall, and Recognition recall. Story length and complexity increased with age of the tested child. All participants completed the Free and Cued Recall tasks, whereas the Recognition Recall condition was administered only to younger children (up to 10 years of age, as specified in the test manual). By including the NEPSY-II subscale, we aimed to explore whether the training produced cross-domain cognitive effects, potentially extending beyond planning abilities that rely on visual support to encompass broader domains of verbal and auditory memory, as well as attentional processes. In fact, the integration of narrative content relies on the ability to maintain coherence and relevance during recall, reflecting the coordination of working memory, attentional shifting, and cognitive inhibition (Korkman et al., 2007).

S3. Non-parametric analyses on delta-scores

For Study 1, we compared Group 1 and Group 2 on their change from T0 to T1 ($\Delta = T1 - T0$) for each dependent variable (BVSCO-3 and NEPSY-II subscales) using Mann–Whitney tests. For these analyses, we report the W statistic, the p value, and the rank-biserial correlation with its standard error and 95% confidence interval.

For Study 2, we examined within-group change in Group 2 by comparing the delta associated with the control period ($\Delta_{\text{control}} = T1 - T0$) and the delta associated with the training period ($\Delta_{\text{training}} = T2 - T1$) using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests. For these analyses as well, we report the test statistic (V), the p value, and the corresponding rank-biserial correlation with its standard error and 95% confidence interval.

It is important to note that, although delta-score analyses can offer an intuitive summary of change within each study of the crossover design, they necessarily collapse two timepoints into a single value and therefore reduce within-subject variance. For this reason, the repeated-measures ANOVAs based on the full longitudinal structure ($T0, T1, T2$) provide the most statistically informative and methodologically sensitive assessment of group trajectories over time. The supplementary non-parametric delta analyses were included to provide study-specific comparisons for completeness and to allow readers to consider the two studies as partially independent segments. Their results should therefore be interpreted as complementary to, rather than replacements for, the primary timepoint-based analyses.

Delta-score results

Study 1

To complement the repeated-measures ANOVA, we compared the change scores from $T0$ to $T1$ ($\Delta = T1 - T0$) between Group 1 (robot-assisted training) and Group 2 (passive control) using Mann-Whitney tests. Results showed that Group 1 exhibited significantly greater improvement on the BVSCO-3 narrative production task ($W = 587.50, p = 0.009, \text{rank-biserial } r = 0.397, SE = 0.152, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.120, 0.617]$). A similar pattern emerged for the NEPSY-II Cued Recall subscale ($W = 549.00, p = 0.026, \text{rank-biserial } r = 0.306, SE = 0.152, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.016, 0.548]$). In contrast, the difference in Free Recall did not reach significance ($W = 526.50, p = 0.076, \text{rank-biserial } r = 0.252, SE = 0.152, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.042, 0.506]$). No between-group difference was observed for the Recognition condition ($W = 451.50, p = 0.581, \text{rank-biserial } r = 0.074, SE = 0.152, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.222, 0.357]$). These findings indicate that, during Study 1, the robot-assisted protocol yielded greater gains than standard therapy in narrative organization and cued verbal reconstruction, but not in recognition-based memory.

Study 2

To examine the effect of the second protocol version, we compared the change scores obtained during the passive-control period ($\Delta_{\text{control}} = T1 - T0$) with those obtained during the robot-assisted period ($\Delta_{\text{training}} = T2 - T1$) within Group 2 using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests. No significant differences emerged for the BVSCO-3 narrative production task ($V = 170.50, p = 0.665, \text{rank-biserial } r = -0.098, SE = 0.217, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.485, 0.322]$), nor for the NEPSY-II Free Recall ($V = 61.00, p = 0.101, \text{rank-biserial } r = -0.419, SE = 0.250, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.738, 0.053]$) or Cued Recall subscales ($V = 72.50, p = 0.372, \text{rank-biserial } r = -0.237, SE = 0.256, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.638, 0.265]$). In contrast, the Recognition condition showed a significant improvement during the robot-assisted period compared with the control period ($V = 25.50, p = 0.016, \text{rank-biserial } r = -0.667, SE = 0.269, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.873, -0.258]$), indicating a selective enhancement in recognition memory associated with the Study 2.

The supplementary delta-score analyses provide additional study-specific context. In Study 1, robot-assisted training yielded larger gains than the passive control for Narrative Production and Cued Recall, consistent with the stronger sequencing focus of the protocol. In Study 2, no differential improvements emerged except for a selective benefit in Recognition during the robot-

assisted period. These results complement the main longitudinal analyses by indicating that transfer effects were shaped by the specific cognitive demands emphasized in each study.

S4. Analysis of Session Number Variability

Rationale and analytical strategy

The robot-assisted intervention was implemented within routine clinical practice, resulting in natural variability in the number of sessions attended by individual children. Some participants completed only a limited number of robot-assisted sessions, with a minimum of three, reflecting real-world rehabilitation schedules rather than protocol deviations. This variability raises a legitimate methodological question as to whether the effects reported in the main manuscript depend on session exposure, and whether excluding children with fewer sessions would materially alter the pattern of results.

To address this issue, we conducted a set of robustness (sensitivity) analyses focusing on Group 1 (G1) during the T0–T1 interval, in line with the analyses described in the main text. Specifically, we examined whether improvements in narrative and memory outcomes were present both in children who completed a short version of the protocol (five or fewer sessions) and in those who completed a longer version (five or more sessions). Previous work in this line of research has already shown that short robot-based interventions can yield measurable cognitive gains; for instance, three sessions were sufficient to produce significant Theory of Mind improvements in autistic children (Ghigino et al., 2025). The aim of these analyses was not to estimate a dose–response relationship, but to verify that the observed effects were consistent across different levels of exposure and therefore not driven by a subset of participants with higher attendance.

Data tables

Table S1 reports individual-level data for children in Group 1 who completed five or fewer robot-assisted sessions (minimum = three).

Table S2 reports individual-level data for children in Group 1 who completed five or more robot-assisted sessions.

In both tables, participant codes are anonymized. Variables including age, gender, IQ, verbal indices, and diagnostic information are provided for descriptive purposes only and were not included in any statistical analyses. Children who completed exactly five sessions are included in both tables by design, as five sessions constituted the boundary between the two exposure definitions. Missing values in the NEPSY-II Recognition condition reflect selective administration rules: according to the test manual, this subscale is administered only when performance on Free and Cued Recall indicates the need for further assessment, and therefore absence of data does not reflect attrition or non-compliance.

Table S1

Individual-level data for children in Group 1 (G1) who completed five or fewer robot-assisted sessions (short exposure).

Co de	BVSCO _PG_T0	BVSCO _PG_T1	NEPSY_ Free_T0	NEPSY_ Cued_T0	NEPSY_ Recog_T 0	NEPSY_ Free_T1	NEPSY_ Cued_T1	NEPSY_ Recog_T 1
BP 00 3	31	38	4	1	1	9	8	8
BP 00 4	18	20	1	1	1	1	1	1
BP 01 1	3	12	1	1	1	1	1	1
BP 01 5	68	74	2	1	1	4	1	5
BP 01 7	20	28	3	1	4	3	1	4
BP 01 8	14	30	2	1	11	7	9	13
BP 02 1	31	54	9	9	10	12	12	12
BP 02 5	21	30	9	8	10	10	8	10
BP 03 0	40	62	1	1	–	6	6	–
BP 03 1	7	8	1	1	1	1	1	1
BP 04 7	45	51	12	8	–	12	10	–
BP 05 0	13	21	3	3	5	5	4	12
BP 05 5	22	27	1	1	–	1	1	–

Note.

This table reports individual pre- (T0) and post-intervention (T1) scores for children in Group 1 who completed five or fewer robot-assisted sessions (minimum = three). BVSCO_PG refers to the Written Narrative Production score of the BVSCO-3. NEPSY_Free, NEPSY_Cued, and NEPSY_Recog refer to the Free Recall, Cued Recall, and Recognition subscales of the NEPSY-II Narrative Memory task, respectively. Dashes indicate that the Recognition subscale was not administered, in accordance with NEPSY-II administration rules for children who do not show difficulties in Free or Cued Recall. Participant codes are anonymized. Descriptive variables such as age, gender, IQ, and diagnostic scores were collected but are not shown here, as they were not included in the analyses.

Table S2

Individual-level data for children in Group 1 (G1) who completed five or more robot-assisted sessions (longer exposure).

Co de	BVSCO_PG_T0	BVSCO_PG_T1	NEPSY_Free_T0	NEPSY_Cued_T0	NEPSY_R_ecog_T0	NEPSY_Free_T1	NEPSY_Cued_T1	NEPSY_R_ecog_T1
BP 001	40	51	10	10	12	13	14	12
BP 003	31	38	4	1	1	9	8	8
BP 004	18	20	1	1	1	1	1	1
BP 011	3	12	1	1	1	1	1	1
BP 018	14	30	2	1	11	7	9	13
BP 020	15	17	4	1	4	5	2	4
BP 024	14	24	1	1	1	1	1	3
BP 025	21	30	9	8	10	10	8	10
BP 029	73	93	5	3	–	6	4	–
BP 030	40	62	1	1	–	6	6	–
BP 031	7	8	1	1	1	1	1	1
BP 032	63	65	8	8	–	10	11	–
BP 040	35	72	8	6	–	8	6	–
BP 044	22	46	3	1	7	3	1	4
BP 046	75	82	1	1	–	1	1	–
BP 050	13	21	3	3	5	5	4	12
BP 054	28	38	8	4	12	11	12	12
BP 055	22	27	1	1	–	1	1	–
BP 058	32	34	10	9	5	10	10	7

Note.

This table reports individual pre- (T0) and post-intervention (T1) scores for children in Group 1 who completed five or more robot-assisted sessions. Children who completed exactly five sessions are included in both Table S1 and Table S2 by design, as five sessions constituted the boundary between exposure definitions in the sensitivity analyses. Variable definitions and administration rules are identical to those described for Table S1.

Variables and measures

Robustness analyses focused on the same dependent variables used in the main manuscript. Narrative production was assessed using the Written Narrative Production task of the BVSCO-3, which captures planning, organization, and monitoring processes during written story construction. Verbal narrative memory was assessed using the NEPSY-II Narrative Memory subtest, considering Free Recall, Cued Recall, and Recognition conditions.

For all variables, within-participant comparisons were performed between baseline (T0) and post-intervention (T1).

Sensitivity analyses by session exposure

All analyses employed two-tailed Wilcoxon signed-rank tests comparing T0 and T1 scores within each subgroup. Rank-biserial correlations produced extreme values in several comparisons due to consistent directionality of paired ranks; for clarity, results are therefore reported using test statistics and p values only.

Short exposure group (≤ 5 sessions)

In the subgroup of children who completed five or fewer robot-assisted sessions, within-participant comparisons revealed a significant improvement in BVSCO-3 Narrative Production scores from T0 to T1 ($z = -3.18$, $p = .002$). Significant improvements were also observed for NEPSY-II Narrative Memory in both the Free Recall condition ($z = -2.37$, $p = .021$) and the Cued Recall condition ($z = -2.20$, $p = .036$).

For the NEPSY-II Recognition condition, the comparison did not reach statistical significance ($z = -2.02$, $p = .057$). Given the small sample size, the selective administration of this subscale, and the number of parallel robustness comparisons conducted, this result is interpreted conservatively and is not considered evidence of a trend.

Overall, children with limited exposure to the robot-assisted protocol showed clear improvements in narrative organization and effortful verbal recall, comparable in magnitude and direction to those observed in the full sample.

Longer exposure group (≥ 5 sessions)

In the subgroup of children who completed five or more robot-assisted sessions, within-participant analyses showed a significant increase in BVSCO-3 Narrative Production scores from T0 to T1 ($z = -3.83$, $p < .001$). Significant improvements were likewise observed for NEPSY-II Free Recall ($z = -2.80$, $p = .006$) and Cued Recall ($z = -2.80$, $p = .006$).

No significant change was observed for the NEPSY-II Recognition condition in this subgroup ($z = -1.36$, $p = .202$).

The pattern of results closely mirrors that observed in the short-exposure group, indicating that improvements in narrative production and effortful recall are present regardless of session count, whereas recognition-based memory remains unaffected.

Conclusion and implications from the analysis of session number variability

These robustness analyses demonstrate that the effects reported in the main manuscript are stable across different levels of session exposure. Both children who completed only a few robot-assisted sessions and those who completed longer versions of the protocol showed significant improvements in narrative production and effortful verbal recall. There is therefore no statistical justification for excluding participants based on the number of robot-assisted sessions attended.

From a clinical perspective, this finding is particularly relevant. Attendance variability is inherent to rehabilitation settings, and children with ASD differ widely in cognitive profiles, learning speed, and responsiveness to structured activities. For some children, especially those without intellectual disability or with stronger verbal abilities, a limited number of interactions may be sufficient to grasp the task structure and benefit from the embodied sequencing activity. Excluding such participants would reduce ecological validity and misrepresent real-world therapeutic practice.

At the same time, these analyses suggest that session exposure may represent a meaningful dimension for future research. Larger samples and designs explicitly targeting learning trajectories could investigate whether distinct cognitive profiles are associated with differential responsiveness or optimal intervention intensity. Addressing these questions, however, lies beyond the scope of the present study, whose primary aim was to establish the robustness of humanoid-assisted training effects under clinically realistic conditions.

S5. Analysis of Age-Based Subgroup Effects

To examine potential age-related differences, the sample was stratified into two subgroups: children aged 6–9 years ($M = 7.91$, $SD = 1.00$, 4 females) and children aged 10–15 years ($M = 11.42$, $SD = 1.59$, 8 females). Below, we report the results for each measure, highlighting the consistency of intervention effects across age groups.

BVSCO-3 – Narrative Abilities

For the 6–9 age group, a within-subjects ANOVA revealed a significant main effect of time ($F(2, 32) = 24.394$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = 0.604$) and a Group \times Time interaction ($F(2, 32) = 7.095$, $p = 0.003$, $\eta^2_p = 0.307$). In Group 1 (G1), scores improved significantly from T0 to T1 (Mean Difference = -10.167 , $SE = 2.226$, $t = -4.568$, $p = 0.001$) and T0 to T2 (Mean Difference = -13.333 , $SE = 2.226$, $t = -5.990$, $p < .001$). For Group 2 (G2), improvements were observed from T1 to T2 (Mean Difference = -5.250 , $SE = 1.574$, $t = -3.336$, $p = 0.032$). In the 10–15 age group, the main effect of time ($F(2, 60) = 14.355$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = 0.324$) and Group \times Time interaction ($F(2, 60) = 3.602$, $p = 0.033$, $\eta^2_p = 0.107$) were also significant. G1 improved from T0 to T1 (Mean Difference = -9.944 , $SE = 2.063$, $t = -4.821$, $p < .001$) and T0 to T2 (Mean Difference = -9.722 , $SE = 2.063$, $t = -4.713$, $p < .001$), while G2 showed a marginal trend from T1 to T2 (Mean Difference = -6.500 , $SE = 2.339$, $t = -2.779$, $p = 0.109$).

NEPSY-II – Narrative Memory (Free Recall)

In the 6–9 age group, the main effect of time was significant ($F(2, 36) = 4.947$, $p = 0.013$, $\eta^2_p = 0.216$), with a trend toward a Group \times Time interaction ($F(2, 36) = 3.091$, $p = 0.058$, $\eta^2_p = 0.147$). G1 showed a marginal improvement from T0 to T2 (Mean Difference = -2.143 , $SE = 0.734$, $t = -2.919$, $p = 0.090$). For the 10–15 age group, the main effect of time was significant ($F(2, 60) = 8.428$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = 0.219$), with G1 improving from T0 to T2 (Mean Difference = -1.278 , $SE = 0.382$, $t = -3.341$, $p = 0.022$).

NEPSY-II – Narrative Memory (Cued Recall)

For the 6–9 age group, the main effect of time ($F(2, 36) = 7.077$, $p = 0.003$, $\eta^2_p = 0.282$) and Group \times Time interaction ($F(2, 36) = 4.366$, $p = 0.020$, $\eta^2_p = 0.195$) were significant. G1 improved from T0 to T1 (Mean Difference = -2.714 , $SE = 0.861$, $t = -3.153$, $p = 0.049$) and T0 to T2 (Mean Difference = -3.143 , $SE = 0.861$, $t = -3.651$, $p = 0.012$). In the 10–15 age group, the main effect of time was significant ($F(2, 60) = 5.460$, $p = 0.007$, $\eta^2_p = 0.154$), with G1 improving from T0 to T1 (Mean

Difference = -1.333, SE = 0.403, $t = -3.305$, $p = 0.024$) and T0 to T2 (Mean Difference = -1.278, SE = 0.403, $t = -3.167$, $p = 0.036$).

Discussion: Generalizability of Intervention Effects

The age-split analyses confirm that the intervention's positive effects on narrative abilities and memory are robust and generalizable across a wide age range (6–15 years). Both subgroups exhibited significant improvements in G1 and minimal/no changes in G2 until after intervention, mirroring the main results. The consistency of these findings—despite developmental differences—supports the intervention's broad efficacy and inclusivity. While the current sample size limits the detection of subtle age-related moderators, the results underscore the potential for broad implementation. Future research with larger samples may further clarify the mechanisms underlying these effects and optimize outcomes for diverse learners. The single-group results remain the most parsimonious representation of the data, but the age-split analyses provide additional evidence of the intervention's applicability across developmental stages.

S6. Qualitative observations

In addition to the quantitative measures reported in the following sections, qualitative observations were collected throughout both studies by the research assistant teleoperating the robot. Across sessions, children generally accepted iCub as a cooperative play partner and engaged readily in the sequencing activity. In Study 1, several participants completed the task accurately but with reduced spontaneity, which clinicians and operators attributed to the slower pace and mechanical rhythm of the robot's movements. Other participants, however, showed consistently high levels of social responsiveness toward the robot. This included echolalic repetition of the robot's phrases, mimicry of its verbal prompts, or the use of filler repetitions while thinking through a response, behaviours that often occur in playful, turn-based interactions. Some children addressed the robot directly with comments such as "you are friendly," asked it personal questions in a conversational manner (for example, its age or where it was from), or responded to the robot's farewell with parting remarks such as "see you soon." Even teasing expressions like calling the robot "dumb" were typically delivered in a light, familiar tone. A few participants also asked when the robot would "go to sleep" or needed to "rest," spontaneously integrating the robot into their imaginative frame.

Mechanical issues occasionally occurred, such as the robot's head freezing in an unusual position, a hand failing to grasp a cube, or an arm moving with reduced fluidity. When these events were minor, the operator provided a playful explanation—for instance noting that the robot had "neck pain" or had "hurt its finger"—whereas more disruptive issues required briefly pausing or restarting the robot. Children generally showed no fear during these moments but often expressed mild concern, asking whether the robot was in pain, reassuring it that they themselves sometimes felt tired or clumsy, or softly singing to it while waiting for it to restart. These reactions were most common among younger participants, who tended to engage with the robot through spontaneous imaginative play.

Older children and adolescents displayed a different pattern. Many immediately recognised that the robot was being teleoperated and occasionally addressed the operator directly, sometimes stating openly that they knew the robot was being controlled. When they were tired or less motivated, their responses to the robot's prompts were shorter or delivered with reduced enthusiasm, although performance remained accurate and clinicians noted that these

fluctuations mirrored their general mood during standard therapy. Among adolescents, the Wizard-of-Oz nature of the setup was evident, and the interaction appeared less immersive, although this did not interfere with their willingness or ability to complete the task.

Overall, the qualitative observations across both studies indicate high tolerability, stable engagement, and the emergence of social, imaginative, or corrective behaviours appropriate to each child's developmental level, with increasing independence in task execution across sessions—a progression that we attribute to growing familiarity with the activity structure and the gradual acquisition of expertise in navigating the sequence-building task.